

IMPLEMENTATION OF CHILD-FRIENDLY REGENCY POLICY AT THE OFFICE OF SOCIAL AFFAIRS, WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT, CHILD PROTECTION, AND FAMILY PLANNING IN LANDAK REGENCY

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Abstract

This thesis aims to analyze the implementation of child-friendly policies at the Social Services, Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning Office of Landak Regency. The problem in this study is that it still faces obstacles in cross-sector coordination that is not optimal. The lack of intensive socialization causes some stakeholders to only understand the policy administratively without embracing the principles of fulfilling children's rights. The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the process of implementing child-friendly policies at the Social Services, Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning Office of Landak Regency, seen from the aspects of organization, interpretation, and application. The research method used is a qualitative approach with data collection techniques through in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation studies. The results of the study indicate that the implementation of the Child-Friendly Child Protection (KLA) policy in Landak Regency at the organizational stage, institutional structure and division of tasks have been formed and are running according to regulations. However, there are still obstacles such as limited resources. At the interpretation stage, socialization and counseling efforts regarding the KLA policy have been carried out to the community, but understanding of the policy is not yet evenly distributed. Meanwhile, at the application or implementation stage, various programs and activities related to the fulfillment of children's rights and protection have been implemented, but their implementation in the field has not been optimal. This research recommends strengthening cross-sector coordination, increasing human resource capacity, and optimizing community outreach and participation to ensure more effective implementation of the Child-Friendly Childcare (KLA) policy in fulfilling and protecting children's rights in Landak Regency.

Keywords: *Implementation, Policy, Child-Friendly.*

1. Introduction

The Child-Friendly Regency Program (Kabupaten Layak Anak/KLA) constitutes one of the government's strategic policies aimed at ensuring the comprehensive fulfillment of children's rights and protection at the regency/city level. As emphasized by Anderson (in Islamy, 2017:30), public policy refers to policies developed by governmental institutions and officials that are oriented toward specific objectives in the interest of society. In this context, the KLA policy is grounded in Law Number 17 of 2016 concerning Child Protection, as well as the Regulation of the Minister of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Number 12 of 2011 regarding Indicators of Child-Friendly Regencies/Cities. Wahab (2014:48) explains that the public policy-making process begins with an awareness of a particular problem or policy issue, which in this case is the inadequate fulfillment of children's rights and protection across various regions. The primary orientation of the KLA is the creation of a child-friendly environment in which children are provided with optimal opportunities to grow and develop, are protected from violence and discrimination, and are able to actively participate in their lives. Leslie A. Pal (in Widodo, 2015:10) categorizes policies based on their goals and impacts, in which the KLA policy encompasses both—namely, the fulfillment of children's rights as its primary objective and tangible improvements in children's lives as indicators of success. At the local level, Regional Regulation of Landak Regency Number 9 of 2020 concerning Child-Friendly Regency serves as the legal foundation for formulating concrete steps toward the implementation of this policy.

The Office of Social Affairs, Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning (SP3AKB) of Landak Regency plays a strategic role in translating this policy into concrete programs and actions, such as cross-sectoral coordination, policy advocacy, the formulation of regional action plans, as well as monitoring and evaluating the implementation of child protection efforts. According to Nugroho (2016:24), implementation is the process of executing plans that have been carefully and systematically prepared. However, based on data from the SP3AKB Office of Landak Regency (January 2026), the implementation of KLA still faces several challenges, including the uneven establishment of Child Forums at the sub-district and village levels, the limited availability of professional personnel such as psychologists, and the insufficient number of Community-Based Integrated Child Protection activists (PATBM) relative to the extensive area that must be covered.

These challenges indicate limitations in resources that affect the effectiveness of policy implementation. Purwanto and Sulistyastuti (2017:134) argue that resources—including the number of staff, implementers' expertise, information, authority, and facilities—are crucial factors in the success of policy implementation. Furthermore, Meter and Horn (in Wibawa, 2014:19) assert that policy implementation is strongly influenced by the behavior of implementing bureaucracies, including their level of understanding of policy objectives. In practice, differences in interpretation among stakeholders often result in policy implementation that is merely administrative and does not fully address the substantive aspects of child protection. Subarsono (2015:18) adds that effective implementation requires a transformation in the government's role from executor to facilitator capable of empowering the community.

Although previous studies have examined public policy implementation, most have focused on general aspects such as program effectiveness, policy evaluation, and macro-level supporting and inhibiting factors, without deeply analyzing the implementation process in terms of organization, interpretation, and application as proposed by Jones (2006). In addition, studies on the implementation of Child-Friendly Regency policies at the local level, particularly in Landak Regency, remain relatively limited and have not specifically explored the dynamics of policy execution at the level of local government agencies as the primary implementers. This condition indicates a research gap that warrants further investigation, particularly in understanding how the KLA policy is practically implemented in the field. Based on the above explanation, the research problem in this study is formulated as follows: "How is the process of implementing the Child-Friendly Regency policy at the Office of Social Affairs, Women's Empowerment, Child Protection, and Family Planning in Landak Regency?"

2. Here is the academic English translation of your text:

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Public Policy Implementation

Policy implementation constitutes a crucial stage that determines whether policy objectives can be realized in practice. Nugroho (2016:24) defines implementation as the execution and application of a plan that has been carefully and systematically formulated. Meter and Horn (in Wibawa, 2014:19) formulate six indicators of effective policy implementation: (1) staff competence and quantity, (2) scope and degree of control, (3) political support, (4) organizational strength, (5) degree of communication openness, and (6) linkage with policymakers. Purwanto and Sulistyastuti (2017:134) emphasize that resource components including the number of staff, implementers' expertise, relevant information, authority, and supporting facilities are prerequisites for ensuring that implementation proceeds as expected. Meanwhile, Subarsono (2015:18) highlights that effective implementation requires a transformation of the government's role from executor to facilitator that empowers the community. Jones (2006:296) divides the implementation process into three interrelated stages. First, organization, which refers to the formation or restructuring of resources, units, and methods to translate policy into expected outcomes. Second, interpretation, which involves translating policy language into operational plans and technical guidelines that are acceptable and implementable. Third, application, which refers to the routine provision of services, payments, or other actions aligned with policy objectives. This framework serves as the analytical foundation of this study, as it enables a systematic and staged mapping of implementation issues.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a descriptive qualitative approach aimed at describing and analyzing the phenomenon of policy implementation in depth (Moleong, 2014). Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews with five categories of subjects: the Head of the SP3AKB Office, the Head of the Division of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, implementing staff, representatives of the Landak Regency Children's

Forum, and parent representatives. In addition to interviews, data were obtained through field observations and documentation studies of policy documents, program reports, and applicable Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). Data analysis follows the model proposed by Miles and Huberman, which consists of three stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing (Sugiyono, 2018). Data validity was ensured through source triangulation and technique triangulation. The research was conducted at the SP3AKB Office of Landak Regency during January–February 2026.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Organizational/Institutional Stage

The organizational stage in the implementation of the KLA policy in Landak Regency has formally been carried out through the establishment of a KLA Task Force involving various local government agencies (OPD), community institutions, the private sector, and the Children's Forum. The SP3AKB Office plays a coordinating role as mandated by Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2020, with an institutional structure referring to the established organizational framework (SOTK). The Head of SP3AKB confirmed this condition, stating:

"The division of roles is clear in accordance with the existing organizational structure. Each division has mutually supportive roles, such as the child protection division focusing on fulfilling children's rights and handling child-related cases, the women's empowerment division supporting family strengthening and child-friendly environments, and other divisions assisting in program coordination, data collection, and reporting."

However, the findings reveal a gap between the formal institutional framework and its operational implementation. The Head of the Division of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection acknowledged that cross-sectoral coordination remains suboptimal, intensive socialization is lacking, and the implementation of KLA programs has not been evenly distributed across all sub-districts and villages. This condition aligns with Meter and Horn's findings (in Wibawa, 2014:19), which highlight organizational strength and communication openness as critical indicators of implementation performance.

The Children's Forum of Landak Regency has been established and functions as a platform for children's participation in supporting KLA implementation. A representative stated that their involvement includes socialization activities, child protection campaigns, and providing input to local government. However, data indicate that out of 156 villages in Landak Regency, only 13 have established village-level Children's Forums, and none of the 13 sub-districts have established sub-district-level forums (SP3AKB Landak Regency, 2026). This indicates that children's participation remains highly limited in scope. This finding is consistent with Agus Suryono's (2024) study in Sinjai Regency, which found that weak coordination structures and uneven institutional distribution constitute major obstacles in the organizational stage. Purwanto and Sulistyastuti (2017:134) assert that without adequate institutional support—including human resources, facilities, and functional coordination mechanisms—policy implementation will not achieve optimal results.

2. Interpretation/Understanding Stage

The quality of policy interpretation among implementers and stakeholders determines the direction of implementation in practice. Wahab (2014:48) emphasizes that consistency and clarity of policy objectives must be effectively communicated to all implementers to ensure alignment of actions with policy intent. The findings of this study indicate significant variation in the level of understanding of the KLA policy among stakeholders.

At the leadership level, the Head of the Office demonstrated a comprehensive understanding, stating:

"The primary objective of the KLA policy is to create a safe, child-friendly environment that supports children's growth and development through the integrated and sustainable fulfillment of children's rights. This policy also aims to ensure that every child is protected from various forms of violence, discrimination, and exploitation, and has adequate access to education, healthcare, and participation in social life."

Implementing staff have understood that KLA requires the fulfillment of five clusters and 24 indicators, as well as multi-stakeholder involvement in accordance with the Regent's Decree No. 300/DSP3AKB/2023. However, the Division Head acknowledged that stakeholders' understanding of these indicators remains limited, resulting in suboptimal contributions from various sectors. This gap confirms Dunn's (2004:132) finding that implementation failure often stems from differing interpretations of policy objectives between policymakers and field implementers.

At the community level, interpretation issues are even more apparent. A Children's Forum representative noted that education on issues such as bullying has not been adequately disseminated in schools. Meanwhile, a parent representative stated that they received information about child protection through socialization activities

but only to the extent of knowing that cases can be reported to the SP3AKB Office. Azwar (2016:34) argues that policy improvement should encompass system, institutional, and individual dimensions simultaneously—a condition not yet fully achieved in the KLA implementation context in Landak Regency. The fact that socialization activities have only reached 4 out of 13 sub-districts indicates that policy interpretation remains partial and uneven. Rinawati (2023), in her study in West Pasaman Regency, found similar results, where limited outreach led to non-uniform understanding among stakeholders, ultimately reducing implementation to mere administrative compliance rather than substantive outcomes.

3. Application Stage

The application stage is where policy is truly tested in practice. Jones (2006:296) defines application as the routine provision of services aligned with policy objectives. This study finds that several programs have been implemented, including child protection socialization, family development initiatives, strengthening the role of the Children's Forum, and the provision of protection facilities such as safe houses and the establishment of the UPTD PPA. The Head of the Office stated:

"The implementation of the KLA policy has been carried out through various programs and activities related to the fulfillment and protection of children's rights. However, the implementation has not yet been optimal due to several constraints, such as limited resources, suboptimal cross-sector coordination, and uneven program distribution across the Landak Regency."

Human resource limitations represent the most critical structural barrier. The SP3AKB Office is supported by only 26 personnel, and the UPTD PPA lacks operational staff. Consequently, although all 20 reported cases of child violence were processed administratively, not all victims received psychological assistance due to the absence of professional psychologists in Landak Regency (SP3AKB Landak Regency, 2026). This indicates that case handling remains procedural and does not yet encompass psychological recovery, which is an integral component of comprehensive child protection. Purwanto and Sulistyastuti (2017:134) warn that inadequate human resources result in incomplete program implementation and ineffective supervision. This situation is exacerbated by unequal service distribution, with child-friendly facilities concentrated in urban areas while rural and remote villages lack adequate infrastructure and access to information. This geographical disparity contradicts Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2020, which mandates prompt, accurate, and comprehensive child protection services. Despite these limitations, the KLA program has produced positive impacts acknowledged by various stakeholders. Representatives of the Children's Forum noted increased opportunities for participation and greater attention to child protection issues, while parents reported increased awareness of children's rights. Fadillah Putra (in Siagian, 2015:112) argues that public policy success depends on both macro-level regulatory frameworks and micro-level operational implementation. These findings suggest that while the macro foundation of KLA policy in Landak Regency is relatively strong, its micro-level implementation still requires significant strengthening.

DISCUSSION

Overall, the implementation of the KLA policy in Landak Regency can be categorized as partial implementation—a condition in which a formal framework exists and some programs have been executed, but the quality and coverage have not yet met regulatory standards. This condition occurs across all three stages: formal organizational structures are established without effective coordination, understanding is concentrated at the leadership level but not evenly distributed among implementers, and programs are implemented without proportional resource support relative to the service scope. These findings are consistent with previous studies. Agus Suryono (2024) in Sinjai Regency found a similar pattern where formal KLA institutions existed but operational effectiveness was constrained by limited human resource capacity. Rinawati (2023) in West Pasaman Regency also identified uneven socialization as a root cause of inconsistent implementation. These similarities indicate that KLA implementation challenges are not merely local technical issues but reflect systemic governance challenges in child protection policy at the regency level. From a theoretical perspective, these findings support the bottom-up approach to policy implementation (Wahyuni, 2015:18), which emphasizes the importance of field-level implementer capacity rather than relying solely on top-down policy design. The comprehensive regulatory design of KLA—consisting of five clusters and 24 indicators—will not produce tangible outcomes without adequate investment in institutional capacity, human resources, and functional coordination mechanisms at the local level. Ekowati (2019:21) asserts that policy implementation is a process of translating formal provisions into practical actions carried out by actors, requiring not only regulatory availability but also actor readiness.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the implementation of the Child-Friendly Regency (KLA) policy at the SP3AKB Office of Landak Regency has been carried out across the three stages—organization, interpretation, and application—but with suboptimal quality. At the organizational stage, formal institutional structures have been established through the KLA Task Force and Children's Forum; however, cross-sectoral coordination and the establishment of forums at sub-district and village levels remain limited. At the interpretation stage, there is a significant gap in understanding between leadership and implementers, as well as between areas reached and not reached by socialization efforts. At the application stage, implemented programs have generated positive impacts recognized by both the Children's Forum and the community; however, they are constrained by human resource deficits—particularly the absence of professional psychologists—and uneven service distribution between urban and rural areas. The practical implications of these findings include the need for: (1) strengthening cross-sectoral coordination through institutionalized and structured coordination meetings; (2) fulfilling human resource needs within the UPTD PPA, including the recruitment of professional psychologists; (3) intensifying community-based socialization covering all 13 sub-districts and 156 villages; and (4) expanding the establishment of Children's Forums at sub-district and village levels as a prerequisite for fulfilling child participation indicators in KLA assessment.

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